

THE DOCTOR

Field advantage:

1 extra point if he/she stops in the Hospital and Pharmacy field.

Expertise advantage:

1 extra point for any challenge solved.

THE LAYWER

Field advantage:

1 extra point if he/she stops in the Court and Police Station field.

Expertise advantage:

1 extra point for any IT-related challenge solved.

RESEARCHER

Field advantage:

1 extra point if he/she stops in the University and Library field.

Expertise advantage:

1 extra point for any RED challenge solved.

DEVELOPER

Field advantage:

1 extra point if he/she stops in the Internet Provider, Telecom Provider, and Digital Platform and Police Station field.

Expertise advantage:

1 extra point for any legal-related challenge solved.

STUDENT

Field advantage:

1 extra point if he/she stops in the Social Network, Streaming Service and Gym field.

Expertise advantage:

1 extra point for any GREEN challenge solved.

ENTREPRENEUR

Field advantage:

1 extra point if he/she stops in the Bank and Post Office field.

Expertise advantage:

1 extra point for any BLUE challenge solved.